

nextGEMS

Next Generation Earth Modelling Systems

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About this document

The report presents a map of the carbon fluxes over Europe as derived from an offline simulation of the carbon fluxes driven by the SR-ESM output.

Work package in charge:

WP9

Lead author:

Cathy Hohenegger

Other contributing authors:

Junhong Lee

Internal reviewer(s):

1st reviewer: Emanuel Dutra

2nd reviewer: Chiel van Heerwaarden

Contacts: cathy.hohenegger@mpimet.mpg.de

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Executive summary

This report presents the deliverable associated with WP9.4, which aimed to quantify the carbon fluxes over Europe, as derived from an offline terrestrial ecosystem simulation, driven by the output of the nextGEMS ICON storm-resolving model, and compare these estimates to estimates obtained from coarse-resolution models. As described in the report, the goal was achieved by comparing the results of two offline terrestrial ecosystem simulations, one driven by the nextGEMS ICON storm-resolving model, one by a conventional coarse-resolution climate simulation taken from CMIP6. Using storm-resolving atmospheric forcing leads in mean to a larger gross primary productivity, meaning that the plants are more actively photosynthesizing. We explain this behavior by the fact that more shortwave radiation is available for plants photosynthesis due to shorter rainfall events in the storm-resolving model. Hence, we were able to show that storm-scale variability affects the carbon budget through its impact on the hydrological cycle, fully achieving project goal vi.

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Objectives

Project objectives

This deliverable contributes to the achievement of the following specific project topics.

The table below outlines the overarching objectives of the nextGEMS. Objectives that the work for the current deliverable contributes to are marked with *yes*.

Specific objectives of the project	Contribution of this deliverable?
O1	
To develop two SR-ESMs for applications	
(i) by demonstrating their capacity to more realistically represent the coupled (land-ocean-atmosphere) climate system, also through an ability to better leverage observations;	no
(ii) by performing the first global multi-decadal (30 y) SR-ESM based climate projections, testing for out-of-sample climate trajectories, i.e., surprises, and thereby giving a new perspective on uncertainty; and	no
(iii) by expanding their scope to begin more physically coupling 'Earth-system' processes, including the carbon cycle and the atmospheric aerosol	yes
O2	
To use SR-ESMs to test emerging and long-standing hypotheses underpinning our understanding of climate change:	
(i) that convective organization contributes importantly to Earth's energy budget and the strength of cloud feedbacks;	no
(ii) that a more explicit representation of cloud-aerosol interactions mutes aerosol-radiative forcing;	no

Specific objectives of the project	Contribution of this deliverable?
(iii) that 2 km to 200 km scale atmospheric and oceanic circulations are of leading order importance for air-sea fluxes in the tropics, thereby influencing not only the mean tropical and mid-latitude climate, but also its variability, including extremes;	no
(iv) that storm-scale variability in weather systems and of the land surface strongly influence extra-tropical climate and extremes, for instance by conditioning circulation regimes, like blocking;	no
(v) that capturing landscape variability globally greatly improves the realism with which regional climate can be simulated; and	no
(vi) that storm-scale variability through its impact on hydrological extremes affects the carbon budget, with associated implications for the global carbon (emissions) stock-take.	yes

O3

To build new, more integrated, communities of ESM users by:

- | | |
|--|----|
| (i) exploiting the necessity of developing SR-ESMs around a centralized infrastructure to create development and analysis paradigms that can more directly involve a broader and more distributed scientific community; and | no |
| (ii) by exploiting the affinity between what people experience and what SR-ESMs simulate (i.e., events, in addition to statistics) to more directly involve non-scientific users in model development, thereby fostering Knowledge Coproduction. | no |

Work package objectives

This deliverable directly contributes to the achievement of specific objectives indicated in the description of the Work Package as indicated below.

Objectives of WP9	Relevance in this deliverable?
Investigate whether resolving the storm-scale variability in weather systems and in the land surface, together with their consistent interactions with the larger scales, affects the climatology of blocking, the statistics of dry and warm spells, the mean surface radiation balance as well as near-term changes in aggregated temperature and precipitation statistics (O2)	no
Quantify the carbon stocks and fluxes over Europe at storm-resolving resolution and compare these estimates to ones from current ESMs (O2)	yes
Use the production runs to reassess solar power on the global scale and to produce global maps of hazardous weather at unprecedented resolution (O3)	no

Synergies

This deliverable was dependent upon task 8.6 and its associated deliverable. In task 8.6, we set up and spun up the offline terrestrial ecosystem simulation and in this task (task 9.4), we analyzed the result of this simulation in terms of carbon fluxes and compared the obtained estimates to a simulation driven by a conventional coarse-resolution climate simulation.

The goal of this deliverable was to use the output of the nextGEMS storm-resolving run of ICON to drive an offline version of the terrestrial ecosystem model JSBACH, set up in task 8.6, to estimate carbon fluxes over Europe. In the past, either full earth system models including the carbon cycle, integrated at coarse resolution ($O(100\text{ km})$), or terrestrial ecosystem models driven by atmospheric forcing from observation or coarse-resolution climate models, have been employed to estimate carbon fluxes. Past studies have shown that the atmospheric forcing plays a dominant role in the carbon fluxes estimation (Schaphoff et al., 2006; Jung et al., 2007; Ahlström et al., 2017; Hardouin et al., 2022). The hypothesis underlying this work was that the expected distinct temperature and precipitation statistics between storm-resolving and coarse-resolution climate simulations should impact the biosphere, and hence carbon fluxes. For the first time, we coupled the output of a storm-resolving model to a terrestrial ecosystem model to investigate this hypothesis.

1 Method

To estimate carbon fluxes over the land, we use the terrestrial ecosystem model JSBACH (Jena Scheme for Biosphere Atmosphere Coupling in Hamburg, see Reick et al., 2021). JSBACH is integrated at a grid spacing of 5 km, over a domain covering Europe (see Fig. 1). The necessary atmospheric forcing is derived from the nextGEMS cycle 3 simulation of ICON. That simulation was integrated for five years at a grid spacing of 5 km (Segura et al., 2025), and we use the last four years as atmospheric forcing. The first year of the ICON simulation is disregarded because of spin-up effects. The terrestrial JSBACH simulation is first integrated cyclically over those four years, with ICON atmospheric forcing, until the carbon pools are equilibrated. Then we integrate the simulation for four more years and use this period for analysing the carbon fluxes. More detail on the set-up of the terrestrial JSBACH simulation and its spin-up was described in the report of task 8.6. In the remainder of this text, we refer to this simulation as SRM, as an abbreviation for storm-resolving model, because the terrestrial simulation was driven by the output of a storm-resolving model.

To assess the impact of storm-resolving atmospheric forcing on carbon estimates, we conduct a second simulation at a grid spacing of 160 km. Here, the required atmospheric forcing is taken from four years of a simulation that was conducted with the MPI Earth System Model. We use the simulation called MPI-ESM1.2-LR.piControl (Wieners et al., 2019), conducted in the context of CMIP6. In contrast to the ICON simulation, MPI-ESM1.2-LR.piControl is a typical coarse-resolution simulation, and serves as an example for typical carbon estimates obtained from past simulations conducted at coarse resolution. The simulation employs a suite of parameterizations, including one for convection, whereas convection is explicitly resolved in ICON. The vegetation and land surface fields required to integrate this second offline terrestrial simulation are derived by downgrading the high-resolution surface fields from 5 km to 160 km. As for the 5-km terrestrial simulation, the simulation is first integrated cyclically over the four years, with MPI-ESM1.2-LR.piControl atmospheric forcing, until the carbon pools are equilibrated. Then we integrate the simulation for four more years and use this period for analysing the carbon fluxes. This simulation is referred to as LR, as it was driven by low-resolution (160-km) atmospheric forcing.

2 Result

2.1 Carbon flux difference between the SRM and the LR

Figure 1 shows the temporally averaged carbon fluxes over Europe obtained for the two terrestrial simulations and their differences. Gross Primary Productivity (GPP) quantifies the amount of CO₂ removed by plants from the atmosphere to fuel their photosynthesis. It is actually the largest of the carbon fluxes on Earth. We see that for GPP, SRM simulates higher values except over south-eastern Europe. Figure 1 also shows how GPP is used by the terrestrial ecosystem: some of it is used to maintain basic functionalities of the plants like photosynthesis, nutrient and water transport, repairs. These processes are collectively called autotrophic respiration (Ra). Some of the GPP is consumed by heterotrophic respiration (Rh). Rh represents "soil" respiration, so respiration by bacteria/fungi in the soil, which happens when such organisms decompose dead organic compounds (litter) to gain energy. Finally some of the GPP is lost by grazing of herbivores (Gr). Figure 1 reveals that Ra and Rh show a similar difference pattern than GPP between the two simulations. We see increased flux in SRM compared to LR over Europe, except over south-eastern Europe. For Gr, the difference pattern is a bit more homogeneous, with generally lower values in SRM compared to LR.

Note that some of the GPP can also be lost by harvesting crops, a process that we didn't consider in our simulations. Note also that as we are considering equilibrium conditions and as the amount of CO₂ in the atmosphere is not changing, the carbon fluxes of the land are in equilibrium with the CO₂ concentration in the atmosphere and there is no extra carbon available for storage (e.g. plant growth) at equilibrium. In other words net ecosystem productivity is zero (GPP-Ra-Rh-Gr=0).

In addition, and as expected from the higher-resolution of the land surface fields, SRM shows much more detailed spatial features in the carbon fluxes than LR (Fig. 1). Small-scale spatial variability is well resolved in SRM, especially along the Alps, Carpathian, Pyrenees, and Scandinavian mountains. Mountains usually have different characteristics of temperature, precipitation and vegetation than flat regions. Mountains are less well resolved at 160 km than at 5 km.

To better quantify the differences in carbon fluxes between SRM and LR, Table 3 reports the mean fluxes, averaged in space and time. The mean carbon fluxes show that the plants in SRM fix more carbon by photosynthesis than the ones in LR. GPP in SRM is 910.08 g C m⁻² yr⁻¹, which is 10.17 g C m⁻² yr⁻¹ larger than in LR. In the mean, autotrophic respiration is also larger in SRM compared to LR, by 35.21 g C m⁻² yr⁻¹, whereas heterotrophic respiration is smaller, by 24.23 g C m⁻² yr⁻¹. In both simulations, more of the GPP is used for Rh than for Ra, but the two respirations become more similar in SRM, where 50% of GPP is used for Rh and 48% for Ra, compared to 53% for Rh and 44% for Ra in LR. The carbon flux resulting from grazing is small (18-19 g C m⁻² yr⁻¹) and the values are similar in the two simulations. We also note that the relative differences between LR and SRM in Ra (9%) and Rh (5%) are larger than GPP (1%).

Figure 1: (a-c) Gross primary productivity (GPP), (d-f) autotrophic respiration (Ra), (g-i) heterotrophic respiration (Rh), and (j-l) carbon loss by grazing of herbivores averaged over four years for (left) coarse-resolution model (LR), (middle) storm-resolving model (SRM), and (right) the resulting difference (SRM-LR).

Table 3: Gross primary productivity (GPP), autotrophic respiration (Ra), heterotrophic respiration (Rh), and carbon loss by grazing of herbivores (Gr) averaged over Europe and four years of each simulation and their difference (in $\text{g C m}^{-2} \text{ yr}^{-1}$).

Variables	LR	SRM	Difference (SRM-LR)
GPP	899.91	910.08	10.17
Ra	399.81	435.02	35.21
Rh	481.2	456.97	-24.23
Gr	18.9	18.1	-0.81

2.2 What causes the differences in carbon fluxes?

To understand the differences in carbon fluxes between SRM and LR, we look separately at GPP, Ra, Rh and Gr and at their underlying controls.

2.2.1 Gross primary productivity

GPP is given by photosynthesis, which is mainly a function of downward shortwave radiation, temperature, and soil moisture in the root zone. Table 4 shows the results of a multiple linear regression between GPP and these three controlling factors. Both in SRM and LR, downward shortwave radiation plays the dominant role (Table 4). In both simulations, the regression coefficient of downward shortwave radiation is larger than 0.5. The downward shortwave radiation itself is related to precipitation as the precipitating clouds block the downward shortwave radiation. Now we know from past intercomparison studies between storm-resolving and coarse-resolution climate models that these two types of model exhibit different characteristics of precipitation (Guichard et al., 2004; Dai, 2006; Sun et al., 2007; Hohenegger et al., 2009; Prein et al., 2015; Keller, 2016). In particular, coarse-resolution models tend to have excessive long-lasting drizzling precipitation due to the use of convective parameterizations, whereas storm-resolving models rather tend to simulate short-lived, more intense, localized storms. Hence we hypothesize that these different precipitation characteristics imprint themselves on the downward shortwave radiation that reaches the surface and consequently on GPP. To test this hypothesis, we analyze the dependency between precipitation, downward shortwave radiation and GPP in the two simulations, see Fig. 2.

Figure 2a shows that for daily precipitation amount smaller than 10 mm day^{-1} , GPP is similar in both simulations. Differences occur for larger daily precipitation amounts, where GPP remains much larger in SRM compared to LR. To further illustrate this distinct behavior depending on precipitation (P) being larger or smaller than 10 mm day^{-1} , we decompose total mean gross primary productivity (\overline{GPP}) into two contributions based on $P=10 \text{ mm day}^{-1}$:

$$\overline{GPP} = \alpha \cdot \overline{GPP}_{p < 10} + (1 - \alpha) \cdot \overline{GPP}_{p \geq 10}, \quad (1)$$

Table 4: Coefficients from the multiple linear regression of GPP with respect to downward solar radiation (SW), air temperature (T_a), and root zone soil moisture (SM) ($GPP = \beta_0 + \beta_{SW} \cdot SW + \beta_{T_a} \cdot T_a + \beta_{SM} \cdot SM$). Each dependent and independent variable is standardized to have zero mean and unit variance.

Simulations	β_0	β_{SW}	β_{T_a}	β_{SM}
LR	0	0.533	0.222	0.165
SRM	0	0.575	0.1	0.193

Figure 2: (a) Daily mean GPP as a function of daily mean precipitation for the LR (orange line) and the SRM (blue line) and histogram of precipitation (bar). (b) Same as (a) but downward shortwave radiation. (c) Histogram of rain hours per day.

where α is the fraction of occurrence when $P < 10 \text{ mm day}^{-1}$, $\overline{GPP}_{P < 10}$ denotes mean gross primary productivity when $P < 10 \text{ mm day}^{-1}$, and $\overline{GPP}_{P \geq 10}$ indicates mean gross primary productivity when $P \geq 10 \text{ mm day}^{-1}$. The values of each term are summarized in Table 5.

Table 5 indicates that the larger GPP in SRM can only be explained by the larger GPP on days with $P \geq 10 \text{ mm day}^{-1}$, as the GPP on days with $P \leq 10 \text{ mm day}^{-1}$ is smaller in SRM than in LR. In $P \geq 10 \text{ mm day}^{-1}$ condition, $(1 - \alpha) \cdot \overline{GPP}_{P \geq 10}$ is $54.12 \text{ g C m}^{-2} \text{ yr}^{-1}$ in SRM, which is larger than in LR ($27.13 \text{ g C m}^{-2} \text{ yr}^{-1}$), by a factor of two. This is mainly due to the larger $\overline{GPP}_{P \geq 10}$, whereas α only shows a small decrease. Notably, $\overline{GPP}_{P \geq 10}$ in SRM is $877.09 \text{ g C m}^{-2} \text{ yr}^{-1}$, compared to only $661.71 \text{ g C m}^{-2} \text{ yr}^{-1}$ in LR. This difference means that photosynthesis is more active in SRM even on heavy precipitation days. We find that downward shortwave radiation difference can explain the difference in $\overline{GPP}_{P \geq 10}$ (see Fig. 2b). In SRM, downward solar radiation does

Table 5: Decomposition of total GPP into two contributions, based on $P = 10 \text{ mm day}^{-1}$ (Eq. 1)

Simulation	GPP	$\alpha \cdot \overline{GPP}_{P < 10}$	$(1 - \alpha) \cdot \overline{GPP}_{P \geq 10}$	α	$\overline{GPP}_{P < 10}$	$\overline{GPP}_{P \geq 10}$
LR	899.91	872.80	27.13	0.959	910.11	661.71
SRM	910.08	855.96	54.12	0.938	912.25	877.09
SRM-LR	10.17	-16.84	26.99	-0.021	2.14	215.38

Table 6: Same as Table 4 but coefficients of R_a with respect to GPP, T_a , and SW ($R_a = \beta_0 + \beta_{GPP} \cdot GPP + \beta_{T_a} \cdot T_a + \beta_{SW} \cdot SW$).

Simulations	β_0	β_{GPP}	β_{T_a}	β_{SW}
LR	0	0.924	0.132	-0.09
SRM	0	0.879	0.189	-0.092

not decrease as precipitation amounts increase, in stark contrast to LR. Therefore, plants in SRM can photosynthesize more due to the stronger downward shortwave radiation arriving at the surface, even on heavy precipitation days. This stronger downward shortwave radiation can be explained by shorter rain hours in SRM (Fig. 2c). 39.9% of the time in SRM, it rains shorter than 12 hours per day, while it is only 19.4% of the time in LR. Raining the whole day only occurs 17.6% in the SRM, compared to 45.2% in LR. This is consistent with our hypothesis of the impact of using or not a convective parameterization on GPP via its control on precipitation characteristics and hence solar radiation.

In $P < 10$ mm day⁻¹ conditions, $\alpha \cdot \overline{GPP}_{p < 10}$ is 855 g C m⁻² yr⁻¹ for SRM and 872.8 g C m⁻² yr⁻¹ for LR, respectively. The difference mainly stems from the fraction of occurrence (i.e., α), not from the value of $\overline{GPP}_{p < 10}$. The $\overline{GPP}_{p < 10}$ in both simulations are very similar with values of 912.25 g C m⁻² yr⁻¹ in SRM and 910.11 g C m⁻² yr⁻¹ in LR. This similarity is consistent with the similar GPP-precipitation functional relationship in the low precipitation range ($P < 10$ mm day⁻¹), as displayed by Fig. 2a.

2.2.2 Autotrophic respiration

Autotrophic respiration consists of dark respiration and growth respiration. In JSBACH, the dark respiration is a function of air temperature and downward shortwave radiation and the growth respiration is proportional to gross primary productivity. Table 6 summarizes the results of the multiple linear regression between R_a and its three controlling factors. From it, we conclude that gross primary productivity is the dominant controlling factor. Its regression coefficient is around 0.9 and much larger than the other two regression coefficients. As shown in Fig. 3, autotrophic respiration increases linearly in both simulations with gross primary productivity and the curves of SRM and LR overlap. Hence, the larger autotrophic respiration in SRM is mainly a consequence of its larger GPP, which is also consistent with the similar difference pattern in GPP and in R_a between SRM and LR, as previously noted on Fig. 1.

2.2.3 Heterotrophic respiration

Heterotrophic respiration is proportional to a climate dependency function, k_{clim} (Thum et al., 2009; 2011; 2020), given by

$$k_{clim} = e^{\beta_1 \overline{T_c} + \beta_2 \overline{T_c}^2} e^{(1-\gamma) \overline{P_m}}, \quad (2)$$

Figure 3: Daily mean Ra as a function of daily mean GPP for LR (orange line) and SRM (blue line) overlaid on a histogram of precipitation (bar).

where $\overline{T_c}$ is the monthly mean air temperature in $^{\circ}\text{C}$, and $\overline{P_m}$ is the monthly mean precipitation in m yr^{-1} . $\beta_1=0.095\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}^{-1}$, $\beta_2=-0.0014\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}^{-2}$, and $\gamma=-1.27\text{ yr m}^{-1}$ are fitted parameters (Thum et al. 2020). Accordingly, heterotrophic respiration is a function of monthly mean air temperature ($\overline{T_a}$) and precipitation (\overline{P}). Therefore, we analyze the analytic solution of k_{clim} in terms of $\overline{T_a}$ and \overline{P} to understand the difference in heterotrophic respiration between the two simulations.

We first explore the analytic solution of k_{clim} to understand the theoretical impact of $\overline{T_a}$ and \overline{P} on k_{clim} , as displayed in Fig. 4. When $\overline{P} < 4\text{ mm day}^{-1}$, k_{clim} increases when $\overline{T_a}$ or \overline{P} increases due to the fact that decomposition is more active in moist and warm conditions. When $\overline{P} \geq 4\text{ mm day}^{-1}$, k_{clim} does not change much when \overline{P} changes and mostly increases when $\overline{T_a}$ increases.

With the insight from the analytic solution of k_{clim} , we investigate the reason for the smaller heterotrophic respiration in SRM ($456.97\text{ g C m}^{-2}\text{ yr}^{-1}$) compared to LR ($481.2\text{ g C m}^{-2}\text{ yr}^{-1}$). Figures 4a, b and c indicate that the cloud of more frequent points (red shading) is shifted towards smaller \overline{P} in SRM. For instance, SRM has more data than LR when $\overline{P} \leq 1.5\text{ mm day}^{-1}$, by 8%. The medians of \overline{P} in both simulations are 1.9 and 2.07 mm day^{-1} , respectively.

Second, concerning the effect of $\overline{T_a}$ on k_{clim} , SRM has more data when $275 < \overline{T_a} < 280\text{ K}$ and when $\overline{T_a} > 290\text{ K}$, whereas LR has more data when $\overline{T_a} < 270$ and when $280 < \overline{T_a} < 290\text{ K}$ (Fig. 4). Likewise, the medians of $\overline{T_a}$ are 281.01 K in SRM and 280.57 K in LR. In contrast to \overline{P} , SRM has more data when $\overline{T_a}$ is warmer, which would favor Rh. However, according to Tang et al., 2020, precipitation is the main driving factor for heterotrophic respiration in latitudes between 25 and 50°N , while temperature becomes the main driving factor in latitude only above 50°N . Moreover, their additional analysis using the results of Hashimoto et al., 2015 and TRENDY model ensembles suggests that precipitation and soil moisture are the main driving factors over the entire Europe. Similarly, our k_{clim} estimated from $\overline{T_a}$ and \overline{P} medians of the two simulations indicates that \overline{P} is the dominant factor over our domain. If only \overline{P} decreases from LR (2.07 mm day^{-1}) to SRM (1.9 mm day^{-1}), k_{clim} decreases by 0.0578 . Then, if $\overline{T_a}$ increases from LR (280.57 K) to SRM (281.01 K), k_{clim} increases only by 0.047 . The change induced by the change in \overline{P} is 60% greater than the change induced by $\overline{T_a}$. Hence, smaller mean monthly precipitation amounts in SRM explain its smaller heterotrophic respiration.

Our above interpretation is further confirmed by looking at the contribution of each bin to the

Figure 4: (a, b) Two-dimensional histogram (shading) of monthly mean air temperature and precipitation in (a) LR and (b) SRM with the analytic solution of the climate dependency function for Rh (contour). (c) The difference in the two-dimensional histogram with two insets: (right) histogram of precipitation and (bottom) temperature. Stars indicate medians of monthly mean air temperature and precipitation in LR (red star) and in SRM (blue star). (d-f) Contribution of each bin to the mean of Rh (Table 3), which is computed as the sum of Rh in each bin divided by the total number of data ($N=8,736$) ($\text{g C m}^{-2} \text{ yr}^{-1}$) in (d) LR (e) SRM and (f) their difference.

total mean of Rh (Fig. 4d-f). Indeed, LR shows much stronger contributions than SRM where k_{clim} is larger. The peak contributions in LR are higher than $4 \text{ g C m}^{-2} \text{ yr}^{-1}$ and occur in the region near the $k_{clim} = 2$ contour line. In contrast, the peak contributions in SRM are smaller than $3.5 \text{ g C m}^{-2} \text{ yr}^{-1}$ and occur in the region near the $k_{clim} = 2$ contour line.

2.2.4 Grazing of herbivores

The carbon loss by grazing of herbivores is similar between the two simulations. The grazing of herbivores in SRM ($18.1 \text{ g C m}^{-2} \text{ yr}^{-1}$) is very slightly smaller than in LR ($18.8 \text{ g C m}^{-2} \text{ yr}^{-1}$). This is so because the grazing of herbivores is proportional to the green carbon pool and the latter is slightly smaller in SRM ($73.36 \text{ g C m}^{-2} \text{ yr}^{-1}$) versus $76.01 \text{ g C m}^{-2} \text{ yr}^{-1}$ in LR.

3 Conclusion

As planned in the task, we investigated the effect of storm-scale variability on carbon fluxes over Europe. To do so, we compared the results of two offline terrestrial ecosystem simulations, one driven by the nextGEMS storm-resolving ICON model, and one by a conventional coarse-resolution climate model taken from CMIP6. We showed that storm-scale variability affects carbon fluxes over Europe: the shorter rain events in the storm-resolving atmospheric forcing lead

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to more shortwave radiation at the Earth's surface, increasing photosynthesis and leading to higher gross primary productivity (GPP). The output of the two simulations are available at: <https://owncloud.gwdg.de/index.php/s/NDSTmDIlpw1M0gL>

4 References

- Ahlström, A., G. Schurgers, and B. Smith (2017). “The large influence of climate model bias on terrestrial carbon cycle simulations”. In: *Environmental Research Letters* 12.1, p. 014004.
- Dai, A. (2006). “Precipitation characteristics in eighteen coupled climate models”. In: *Journal of climate* 19.18, pp. 4605–4630.
- Guichard, F., J. Petch, J.-L. Redelsperger, P. Bechtold, J.-P. Chaboureaud, S. Cheinet, W. Grabowski, H. Grenier, C. Jones, M. Köhler, et al. (2004). “Modelling the diurnal cycle of deep precipitating convection over land with cloud-resolving models and single-column models”. In: *Quarterly Journal of the Royal Meteorological Society: A journal of the atmospheric sciences, applied meteorology and physical oceanography* 130.604, pp. 3139–3172.
- Hardouin, L., C. Delire, B. Decharme, D. M. Lawrence, J. E. Nabel, V. Brovkin, N. Collier, R. Fisher, F. M. Hoffman, C. D. Koven, et al. (2022). “Uncertainty in land carbon budget simulated by terrestrial biosphere models: the role of atmospheric forcing”. In: *Environmental Research Letters* 17.9, p. 094033.
- Hashimoto, S., N. Carvalhais, A. Ito, M. Migliavacca, K. Nishina, and M. Reichstein (2015). “Global spatiotemporal distribution of soil respiration modeled using a global database”. In: *Biogeosciences* 12.13, pp. 4121–4132.
- Hohenegger, C., P. Brockhaus, C. S. Bretherton, and C. Schär (2009). “The soil moisture–precipitation feedback in simulations with explicit and parameterized convection”. In: *Journal of Climate* 22.19, pp. 5003–5020.
- Jung, M., M. Vetter, M. Herold, G. Churkina, M. Reichstein, S. Zaehle, P. Ciais, N. Viovy, A. Bondeau, Y. Chen, et al. (2007). “Uncertainties of modeling gross primary productivity over Europe: A systematic study on the effects of using different drivers and terrestrial biosphere models”. In: *Global Biogeochemical Cycles* 21.4.
- Keller, M. (2016). “The diurnal cycle of Alpine summer convection in a convection-resolving model: Evaluation with satellite data and sensitivity to atmospheric forcing”. PhD thesis. ETH Zurich.
- Prein, A. F., W. Langhans, G. Fosser, A. Ferrone, N. Ban, K. Goergen, M. Keller, M. Tölle, O. Gutjahr, F. Feser, et al. (2015). “A review on regional convection-permitting climate modeling: Demonstrations, prospects, and challenges”. In: *Reviews of geophysics* 53.2, pp. 323–361.
- Reick, C. H., V. Gayler, D. Goll, S. Hagemann, M. Heidkamp, J. E. Nabel, T. Raddatz, E. Roeckner, R. Schnur, and S. Wilkenskjaeld (2021). “JSBACH 3-The land component of the MPI Earth System Model: documentation of version 3.2”. In.
- Schaphoff, S., W. Lucht, D. Gerten, S. Sitch, W. Cramer, and I. C. Prentice (2006). “Terrestrial biosphere carbon storage under alternative climate projections”. In: *Climatic change* 74, pp. 97–122.
- Segura, H. et al. (2025). “nextGEMS: entering the era of kilometer-scale Earth system modeling”. In: *EGUsphere* 2025, pp. 1–39. DOI: [10.5194/egusphere-2025-509](https://doi.org/10.5194/egusphere-2025-509).
- Sun, Y., S. Solomon, A. Dai, and R. W. Portmann (2007). “How often will it rain?” In: *Journal of Climate* 20.19, pp. 4801–4818.

- Tang, X., S. Fan, M. Du, W. Zhang, S. Gao, S. Liu, G. Chen, Z. Yu, and W. Yang (2020). “Spatial and temporal patterns of global soil heterotrophic respiration in terrestrial ecosystems”. In: *Earth System Science Data* 12.2, pp. 1037–1051.
- Wieners, K.-H., M. Giorgetta, J. Jungclaus, C. Reick, M. Esch, M. Bittner, S. Legutke, M. Schupfner, F. Wachsmann, V. Gayler, H. Haak, P. de Vrese, T. Raddatz, T. Mauritsen, J.-S. von Storch, J. Behrens, V. Brovkin, M. Claussen, T. Crueger, I. Fast, S. Fiedler, S. Hagemann, C. Hohenegger, T. Jahns, S. Kloster, S. Kinne, G. Lasslop, L. Kornblueh, J. Marotzke, D. Matei, K. Meraner, U. Mikolajewicz, K. Modali, W. Müller, J. Nabel, D. Notz, K. Peters-von Gehlen, R. Pincus, H. Pohlmann, J. Pongratz, S. Rast, H. Schmidt, R. Schnur, U. Schulzweida, K. Six, B. Stevens, A. Voigt, and E. Roeckner (2019). *MPI-M MPI-ESM1.2-LR model output prepared for CMIP6 CMIP piControl*. DOI: [10.22033/ESGF/CMIP6.6675](https://doi.org/10.22033/ESGF/CMIP6.6675).